

Estd. 1919

DR. V KRISHNAMURTHY
Educational Foundation
— TIRUCHIRAPPALLI —

**PROCEEDINGS OF
THE NATIONAL CONFERENCE
ON
THE ROLE OF DIGITAL LIBRARY IN
CONSTRUCTING THE DIGITAL WORLD
(NCT-ALA: 2023)**

Editor and Compiler
Dr. T. SURESHKUMAR

Organized by

**Department of Library and Information Science
National College (Autonomous),
Tiruchirappalli-620001**

and

**ALA - Academic Library Association,
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THE ROLE OF DIGITAL LIBRARY IN CONSTRUCTING THE DIGITAL WORLD

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**An Analysis of E-Content Modules on Knowledge Organization and Processing:
Classification and Cataloguing in Library and Information Science with Special
Reference to E-PG Pathshala**

By

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ABSTRACT

The E-PG Pathshala is an open education resource developed by INFLIBNET and the University Grants Commission (UGC) that provides comprehensive information on various papers in the field of Library and Information Science. One such paper is "Knowledge organization and processing: classification and cataloguing," which covers the important aspects of organizing and cataloguing information in libraries. This paper includes a total of 60 e-content modules that are available to students, teachers, LIS professionals, and other interested individuals. This study examines the coverage of these e-content modules to determine whether they provide sufficient information and knowledge on Knowledge organization and processing: classification and cataloguing for libraries. The study aims to raise awareness among students and professionals about the e-content modules available and to identify any gaps or areas for improvement. Identifies e-content modules that facilitate the use of technology. The results of this study indicate that the e-content modules provide comprehensive coverage of the paper's topics, with the exception of some modules that lack self-learning videos.

Key words:E-PG Pathshala, INFLIBNET, E-Resources, Open Educational Resources, Classification and Cataloguing

1. INTRODUCTION

E-PG Pathshala is an e-learning platform developed by MHRD and the National Mission on Education through ICT (NME-ICT). It provides e-content for 77 subjects in the form of text, video, and quizzes, covering a range of disciplines such as sciences, arts, fine arts, humanities, natural and mathematical sciences, linguistics, and languages. Library and information science (LIS) is a crucial subject within the social sciences and is available on e-PG Pathshala with a total of 15 papers containing 393 modules. Knowledge organization and processing: classification and cataloguing for libraries is a particularly important area within LIS education. This paper includes several significant modules, such as Classification and Indexing, library catalogue, classification system and its components, and Meta data and Dublin core. These modules are accessible in the form of text, videos, and quizzes.

2. Review of Literature

Chattopadhyay and Halder. (2021) examined the paper "Informetrics and Scientometrics" of the broad subject "Library and Information Science," which covered all aspects like contributors' types of contributions and institutional contributions. Jeyapragash, RajKumar and Muthuraj (2017) investigate that by major subjects and sub categories of major subjects. It is found that total 15416 modules has contributed by 6 major subjects and further it found that in major subject category the Social Sciences has contributed 5917 Modules and Medical and Health Sciences contributed only 483 modules. Gunaseelan, Sumathi and Ranganathan (2022) investigates the e-content modules of the Library and Information Science in e-PG Pathshala and analyses the contribution of the number of modules, number of papers, and number of experts. The contents (text, video, and quizzes) are also analysed.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To find out the contributors and their types of contribution
- To examine the institution-wise contributions
- To find out the availability of contents in the modules.

4. METHODOLOGY

The study's data was obtained from the E-PG Pathshala website at <https://epgp.inflibnet.ac.in/>. The subject chosen for analysis was "library and information science," and the paper chosen was "Knowledge organization and processing: classification and cataloguing," which consisted of 60 modules. Each module contained E-Text and

LearnMore documents as well as Self-Learning video content for learning. The availability of quizzes was assessed at <https://ugcmoocs.inflibnet.ac.in/quiz/>. The data were analyzed using MS Excel.

5. DATA ANALYSIS

5.1. Description of the Study

The paper titled "Knowledge Organization and Processing: Cataloguing and Classification" comprises various modules that have been authored by distinguished individuals such as retired professors, professors, associate professors, assistant professors, librarians, and deputy librarians. These modules have been created through a series of steps, including paper coordination, content development and subject review. Throughout this process, the principal investigator and subject coordinator have played an active role. Table-1 below presents a comprehensive list of all the modules that fall under this paper.

Table-1:Description of the Study

Modules in Cataloguing	Knowledge Organization and Processing: Cataloguing	Modules in Classification	Knowledge Organization and Processing: Classification
M-1	Library Catalogue – definition, function, importance and adjuncts	M-1	Classification as a logical process and Daily Activity
M-2	History of Catalogue Codes	M-2	Purpose, functions and limitations of bibliographic classification
M-3	Normative Principles: Laws, Canons and Principles – Part I	M-3	Species of bibliographic classification: Enumerative and Faceted
M-4	Normative Principles: Laws, Canons and Principles – Part II	M-4	Classification System and its Components
M-5	Forms of Catalogue: Physical Forms, OPAC and Inner Form	M-5(1)	Work in the idea plane: canons of characteristics
M-6	Subject Cataloguing: Definition, Subject Headings, LC List of Subject Headings and Scar’s List of Subject Headings	M-5(2)	Work in the idea plane: Formation or arrays and chains
M-7	Subject Cataloguing: Chain procedure, POPSI and Precis	M-5(3)	Work in the idea plane: Principles of helpful sequence
M-8	Cooperative Cataloguing, Centralized cataloguing and	M-5(4)	Work in the verbal plane: Cannons Terminology

	Union Catalogue and Precipis		
M-9	Organization of Cataloguing Department	M-6	Notation: kinds, qualities, mnemonics and Hospitality
M-10	Filing Rules: ALA filing rules and Ranganathan's filing rules	M-7	Subject and disciplines: Modes of formation of Subjects
M-11	Type of entries of classified catalogue according to CCC	M-8	Subjects: Basic, compound and complex: Phase relations
M-12	Type of entries of dictionary catalogue according to AACR-2R	M-9	Main classes and their order: Mapping of the universe of knowledge in Major systems of classification
M-13	Rendering of headings CCC and AACR-2; Personal authorship and shared authorship and works produced under editorial direction	M-10	Isolates and auxiliaries: Common and Special isolates; Standard subdivisions
M-14	Cataloguing practice: personal and shared authorship in CCC and AACR-2	M-11	Fundamental categories: facets and facet analysis
M-15	Rendering of headings and cataloguing practice of Pseudonym	M-12(1)	Introduction to major classification systems: Structure & features of DDC
M-16	Corporate authorship in CCC and AACR-2R: Government	M-12(2)	Introduction to major classification systems: Structure & features of Colon Classification
M-17	Cataloguing Practice: Government Publications in CCC and AACR-2R	M-12(3)	Introduction to major classification systems: Structure & features of the Universal Decimal Classification
M-18	Corporate authorship in CCC & AACR-2R: Institution and its Organs	M-12(4)	Introduction to major classification systems: Structure & features of Library of Congress Classification
M-19	Cataloguing Practice: Institution and its organs according to CCC and AACR-2R	M-13(1)	Call, book and collection numbers: use of cutter author tables
M-20	Corporate authorship in CCC and AACR-2R: Conference	M-13(2)	Call, book and collection numbers: Ranganathan's Chronological System
M-21	Cataloguing practice: conference and its organs in CCC and AACR-2R	M-13(3)	Call, book and collection numbers: Shelf arrangement

M-22	Choice and rendering of headings: resolving conflict of authorship in CCC & AACR-2R	M-14	Designing of depth classification schedule: phases and steps
M-23	Multivolume books in CCC & AACR-2R	M-15	Choice of classification scheme: General versus special schemes
M-24	Cataloguing Practice: Multi Volume book in CCC and AACR-2R	M-16	Classification and Indexing
M-25	Composite books in CCC and AACR-2R	M-17	Classification and information Technology: Role of classification in organizing and searching the www
M-26	Cataloguing practice: Composite books in CCC and AACR-2R	M-18	Knowledge organisations: ISKO, CRG and EDUG, etc
M-27	Periodical and serial publication on CCC & AACR-2R		
M-28	Cataloguing practice of periodical and serial publications in CCC and AACR-2R		
M-29	Cataloguing of special materials and electronic resources according to AACR-2R (1988 & 2002)		
M-30	Illustrative examples of cataloguing of special materials & electronic resources according to AACR-2R- 1988 REV & 2002 ED.		
M-31	Latest trends in Bibliography description and Exchange formats: ISBD & CCF		
M-32	Functional Requirements for bibliographic records (FRBR)		
M-33	Resource Description and access (RDA)		
M-34	Meta data and Dublin Core		

In all cases of module preparation, Dr.JagdishArora, Director of INFLIBNET, played the role of Principal Investigator and Subject Coordinator's, Dr.S.P.Soodand Dr.M.P.SatijaRetd Associate Professor of University of Rajasthan and Professor of Guru Nanak Dev University,played the role of paper coordinator in all modules.

5.2. Distribution According to the Contributors

According to table 2, Dr. S.P. Sood and Dr. M.P. Satija have the highest number of coordinated modules in the paper, with Dr. S.P. Sood coordinating 34 modules and Dr. M.P. Satija coordinating 26 modules. In total, there are 12 contributors and experts who have

created 60 modules for the paper. The top three content writers are Dr. M.P. Satija (26), Dr. S.P. Sood (26), and Dr. P.K. Choudhary (4). The last parameter in the table represents the content reviewer. Among all contributors, Dr. S. Ravi has reviewed the most content with a total of 27, followed by Dr. A. Shrimurugan who has reviewed 11 contents, and Dr. S.P. Sood who has reviewed 8 contents. The remaining contributors did not make any contributions in terms of content review. Therefore, out of the 12 contributors, 2 experts contributed to paper coordination, 6 contributors were content writers, and 7 contributors were content reviewers.

Table 2: Distribution According to the Contributors

S.No	Contributors	Types of Contribution		
		Paper Coordinator	Content Writer	Content Reviewer
1	Dr. M.P.Satija	26	26	-
2	Dr. S.V R.Varalakshmai	-	-	05
3	Dr. S.Ravi	-	-	27
4	Dr. A.Shrimurugan	-	-	11
5	Dr. S.P.Sood	34	26	08
6	Dr.Dalbir Singh	-	01	-
7	Dr. S.S.Agarwal	-	03	-
8	Dr. Dinesh Gupta	-	-	04
9	Dr. S.Srinivasaragavan	-	-	02
10	Dr. P.Ganesan	-	-	02
11	Dr. P.K.Choudhary	-	04	-
12	Mr.TarunMondal	-	02	-

5.3. Contributions according to Institution

According to table 3, it is evident that the University of Rajasthan made the highest contribution to paper coordination with a total of 34 modules, while Guru Nanak Dev University followed closely with 26 modules. In terms of content writing, the University of

Rajasthan had the highest number of contributions with 27 contents, while Guru Nanak Dev University and Sambalpur University contributed 26 and 4 contents respectively. Additionally, Annamalai University had the highest level of involvement in the content review process with 27 contributions, followed by Madurai Kamaraj University with 11 contributions and University of Rajasthan with 8 contributions.

Table 3: Contribution according to Institution

S.No	Name of the Institution	Types of Contribution		
		Paper Coordinator	Content Writer	Content Reviewer
1	Alagappa University	-	-	02
2	Andhra University	-	-	05
3	Annamalai University	-	-	27
4	Bharathidasan University	-	-	02
5	Guru Nanak Dev University	26	26	-
6	Jadavpur University	-	02	-
7	Madurai Kamaraj University	-	-	11
8	Sambalpur University	-	04	-
9	University of Rajasthan	34	27	08
10	VaradhmanMahaveer, Open University	-	-	04
11	Vikram University	-	03	-

Availability of Contents in Modules

Table 4 presents an analysis of the module contents available in both text and video formats, which include E-Text, Learn More, Self-Learning, and Quiz. However, it is observed that Module 17 Cataloguing Practice: Government Publications in CCC & AACR-2R and Module 12(4) Introduction to major classification systems: Structure & features of Library of Congress Classification, do not have video lectures in the self-learning format.

Table 4: Availability of Contents

S. No	Cataloguing Modules	Classification Modules	Contents			
			E-Text (Text)	Learn More (Text)	Self-Learning (Video)	Quiz
1	M-1	M-1	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
2	M-2	M-2	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
3	M-3	M-3	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
4	M-4	M-4	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
5	M-5	M-5(1)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
6	M-6	M-5(2)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
7	M-7	M-5(3)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
8	M-8	M-5(4)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
9	M-9	M-6	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
10	M-10	M-7	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
11	M-11	M-8	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
12	M-12	M-9	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
13	M-13	M-10	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
14	M-14	M-11	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
15	M-15	M-12(1)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
16	M-16	M-12(2)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
17	M-17	M-12(3)	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
18	M-18	M-12(4)	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
19	M-19	M-13(1)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
20	M-20	M-13(2)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
21	M-21	M-13(3)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
22	M-22	M-14	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
23	M-23	M-15	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
24	M-24	M-16	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
25	M-25	M-17	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
26	M-26	M-18	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
27	M-27	-	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
28	M-28	-	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
29	M-29	-	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
30	M-30	-	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
31	M-31	-	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
32	M-32	-	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
33	M-33	-	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
34	M-34	-	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

FINDINGS

🚩 Dr. S.P. Sood and Dr. M.P. Satija have the highest number of coordinated modules in the paper. In total, there are 12 contributors and experts who have created 60 modules for the paper.

- ✚ The top three content writers are Dr. M.P. Satija, Dr. S.P. Sood, and Dr. P.K. Choudhary and Dr. S. Ravi has reviewed the most content among all contributors, followed by Dr. A. Shrimurugan and Dr. S.P. Sood.
- ✚ Out of the 12 contributors, 2 experts contributed to paper coordination, 6 contributors were content writers, and 7 contributors were content reviewers.
- ✚ The University of Rajasthan had the highest contribution to paper coordination with a total of 34 modules. Guru Nanak Dev University followed closely with 26 modules in paper coordination.
- ✚ The University of Rajasthan had the highest number of contributions with 27 contents in terms of content writing. Guru Nanak Dev University and Sambalpur University contributed 26 and 4 contents respectively in terms of content writing.
- ✚ Annamalai University had the highest level of involvement in the content review process with 27 contributions. Madurai Kamaraj University had 11 contributions in the content review process. University of Rajasthan had 8 contributions in the content review process.
- ✚ Module 17 Cataloguing Practice: Government Publications in CCC & AACR-2R and Module 12(4) Introduction to major classification systems: Structure & features of Library of Congress Classification do not have video lectures in the self-learning format.

CONCLUSION

The pandemic has highlighted the increasing importance of e-learning and open educational resources, which are beneficial to students worldwide. One such resource is e-PG Pathshala, which offers authentic and free educational materials that are useful not only for academic purposes but also for competitive exams. Despite its usefulness, many students are unaware of the portal and its offerings, particularly with regards to the paper on Knowledge Organization and Processing: Classification and Cataloguing for libraries. Previous studies have explored the availability of modules and experts, as well as the contents of e-PG Pathshala. However, this current study goes further by examining how the availability of papers and modules affects the availability of contents and criticizes the lack of available materials. The study aims to strengthen e-PG Pathshala and promote knowledge enhancement for students towards building a better nation.

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